

Project co-funded by the European Union under the SBEP 2023 First Joint Transnational Co-Funded Call

Project Acronym: ARCFISH

Project Full Title: Digital Twin of the Ocean for Arctic Fisheries

Project Coordinator: Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC)

Deliverable 2.1

Data ingestion services V1

Work-package	WP2 Data ingestion services
Task	Task 2.1: Ingestion services for in situ oceanographic data Task 2.2: Ingestion services for met-ice-ocean model products Task 2.3: Ingestion services for ecosystem model products and biological data Task 2.4: Ingestion services for fishery-dependent and resource management data
Deliverable leader	NERSC
Authors	Torill Hamre (NERSC), Janus Larsen (AU), Marie Maar (AU), Vibe Schourup-Kristensen (AU), Arne Johan Hestnes (KD), Agnieszka Beszczyńska-Möller (IOPAN), Ilona Goszczko (IOPAN), Valur N. Gunnlaugsson (Matis)
Reviewers	Ruth Higgins (EurOcean)
Version	1.0
Due date	31.03.2025
Submission date	31.05.2025
Revision date	(only use for revised version of deliverable)
Dissemination level	PU - Public

Revision history

Version	Date	Change record	Responsible
0.1	24.02.2025	Document outline	NERSC
0.2	23.04.2025	First draft	NERSC
0.3	16.05.2025	Review of first draft	EurOcean
0.4	23.05.2025	Second draft	NERSC
0.5	30.05.2025	Review of second draft	EurOcean
1.0	31.05.2025	Final QA and approved for delivery	NERSC

Copyright

© ARCFISH Consortium. Copies of this deliverable – also of extracts thereof – may only be made with reference to this deliverable.

Citation

Hamre, T., Larsen, J., Maar, M., Schourup-Kristensen, V., Hestnes, A. J., Beszczyńska-Möller, A., Goszczko, I., Gunnlaugsson, V. N. (2025). Data ingestion services V1. ARCFISH Deliverable 2.1. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15564651>

Executive Summary

This document describes the first version of the Data ingestion services for the ARCFISH project funded by the Research Councils of Norway (Research Council of Norway (RCN)), Portugal (Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT)), Poland (The National Centre for Research and Development, Poland (NCBR)), Denmark (Innovation Fund Denmark (IFD)) and Iceland (The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS)), after successful evaluation of the proposals for the 2023 First Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership Joint Transnational Co-Funded Call. The document describes the data ingestions services developed in the first year of the ARCFISH project.

ARCFISH will develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) supporting sustainable fisheries in the Arctic. The DTO will be based on the existing Blue Insight platform that seamlessly supports the market segments of the ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy (Heslop et al., 2022). The New Blue Economy, also known as the Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE), is a concept that promotes sustainable development and conservation of ocean resources for economic, social, and environmental benefits. In the Arctic, sustainable fisheries focusing on achieving long-term sustainability and resilience of ocean ecosystems and communities is the key to uphold good living conditions for its residents. However, the negative impacts of traditional economic activities such as overfishing, marine pollution, habitat destruction, and climate change have threatened the health and sustainability of the ocean, leading to declining fish stocks, loss of biodiversity, and increased coastal vulnerability to natural disasters. New data products and services, co-developed with relevant stakeholders, are needed to provide a better basis for decision-making in fisheries planning and management. For example, for Disko Bay, western Greenland, ecosystem indices based on an improved ecosystem model could include monthly spatial maps of zooplankton biomass and production, benthos biomass, shrimp biomass, and upwelling areas. Data collected around Iceland towards the Barents Sea onboard fishing vessels and in seafood processing could be implemented in the DTO to support relevant stakeholders. For the Arctic in general, potential new services could include advanced eLogbooks and spatiotemporal pattern detection and visualisation. For cost-efficiency these services must leverage novel digital technologies such as DTOs to acquire, process, analyse and visualise heterogeneous data from a wide range of sources.

More information on the project can be found at: <https://www.arcfish.eu/>.

Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1. Background.....	7
1.2. Organisation of the document	7
2. Short introduction on the ingestion services.....	8
3. Ingestion services for in situ oceanographic data.....	10
3.1. In situ oceanographic data from IOPAN AREX cruises.....	10
3.2. In situ oceanographic data from Copernicus MDS (CORA analysed fields, CORA Near Real Time dataset).....	12
3.3. In situ oceanographic data from Argo floats.....	15
3.4. In situ oceanographic data downloaded from GEM.....	15
4. Ingestion services for met-ice-ocean model products.....	18
4.1. CMEMS Topaz forecast products	18
4.2. CMEMS Wind-Wave forecast product.....	19
4.3. Overlaying model products in the 3D Scene builder.....	19
5. Data ingestion services for remote sensing data	20
5.1. Ocean parameters from satellite remote sensing.....	20
6. Ingestion services for ecosystem model products.....	21
7. Ingestion services for fishery-dependent and resource management data.....	22
8. Summary and next steps.....	24
9. References.....	25

List of Figures

Figure 1 THREDDS Client Integration diagram.....	8
Figure 2 The data loading screen integrates several sources.....	9
Figure 3 The data loader screen present multiple options for the user.....	9
Figure 4 Sea ice thickness loaded as layers into the scene. If the data has a time component, it can also replay the time.....	10
Figure 5 Mean temperature of the Atlantic layer measured during the AREX cruises and shown for stations occupied in 2019 and 2023 using Blue Insight Ocean View. Note that the colour scale is different for each year.....	11
Figure 6 Mean salinity of the Atlantic layer measured during the AREX cruises and shown for stations 2023 using Blue Insight Ocean View. Other years can be displayed by switching different layers on/off Note that the colour scale is different for each year.....	11
Figure 7 Mean temperature of the Atlantic layer measured during the AREX cruises and shown for all stations occupied in 2000-2023 using Blue Insight 3D Map. For each station the full set of associated variables can be displayed by selection the station dot with the cursor. Time filter in the lower bottom corner shows time of measurements and allows for selecting a subset of data. The background colour shows ocean bathymetry (GEMCO), available as a separate layer in 3D Map.....	12
Figure 8 CORA NRT temperature and salinity data at depth of 1m loaded as layers into the scene. Temperature in January 2024 is displayed. The data has a time component and can be shown for other months of 2024.....	13
Figure 9 CORA NRT temperature and salinity data at depth of 1m loaded as layers into the scene. Salinity in January 2024 is displayed. The data has a time component and can be shown for other months of 2024.....	14
Figure 10 CORA NRT temperature data at depth of 1m and 300m loaded as layers into the scene. The datasets have a time component and are displayed for April 2024.....	14
Figure 11. Map showing the location of the Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) station in Disko Bay, Greenland (yellow point).....	15
Figure 12. Visualisation of temperature at the depth of 10 m from all GEM cruises in Disko Bay in 2018-2024 in the Blue Insight. Data from all cruises have been collated into one GeoJSON file. Details for each station can be displayed to show measurement date, depth (while the GeoJSON file includes all measured depths, a single depth can be extracted with a user-defined filter), and measured variables (temperature and salinity).	17
Figure 13. Visualisation of salinity at the depth of 10 m from GEM cruises in Disko Bay in 2018 and in 2024 in the Blue Insight. Each year of the cruise data is uploaded as a separate layer what allows to display a single year or a combination of different years at the same map. Note that salinity colour scale is different for each year, this will be unified in future version of Blue Insight.	17
Figure 14. Visualisation of sea surface temperature forecast from the TOPAZ5 model in Blue Insight, including trawling activity data from the Brim fishery, marked as short lines in the visualization.....	18
Figure 15. Visualisation of significant wave height forecast from WAM model in Blue Insight loaded from the OPeNDAP servers.....	19
Figure 16 Model forecasts integrated into the Blue Insight 3D Scene builder. Here illustrated by the Arctic Subpolar gyre sTate Estimate (ASTE) and the Disko Bay model datasets.....	20
Figure 17 Integration of CMEMS wave data into Blue Insight.....	21
Figure 18 Disco Bay model integrated into the Blue Insight Environment.....	22
Figure 19 Vessel movement and trawl data from Trackwell displayed in Blue Insight	23
Figure 20 Replay functionality displaying the fishing vessel movement	23
Figure 21 The combination of ecosystem modelling and fisheries data	24

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
ACDD	Attribute Convention for Data Discovery
AIS	Automatic Identification System
ARC-MFC	Marine Arctic Monitoring and Forecasting Center
Blue-Cloud2026	A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters
CF	Climate and Forecast convention
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth
DCC	Digital Curation Centre
DIF10	Directory Interchange Format version 10
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
FCT	Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT)
eCUDO	Electronic Oceanographic Data Centre (Poland)
EDITO	European Digital Twin Ocean
GEM	Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring
IFD	Innovation Fund Denmark
ILIAD	Integrated digital solution facilitates access to oceanic data and boosts decision-making
In Situ TAC	Copernicus Marine In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre
INTAROS	Integrated Arctic observation system
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NCBR	The National Centre for Research and Development, Poland
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NIRD	National Infrastructure for Research Data (Norway)
NMDC	Norwegian Marine Data Centre
NRT	Near Real Time
OceanSITES	Ocean Reference Stations (sustained observatory network)
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OPeNDAP	Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol
PI	Principal Investigator
RANNIS	The Icelandic Centre for Research, Iceland
RCN	Research Council of Norway
SBE	Sustinal Blue Economy
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
THREDDS	Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Services
TOR	Task Orchestrator fRamework
WAM	WAve Model

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

ARCFISH will develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) Platform delivering new data products and services in support of sustainable Arctic Fisheries. These data products and services will be co-designed with stakeholders in the fisheries sector and used to create products such as ecosystem indices that can be applied in fisheries planning and management. Available data sources and gaps will be analysed to fulfil user needs and ingest relevant data into the Blue Insight DTO Platform. They include (1) oceanographic data from research vessels, autonomous mobile platforms, fixed buoys, and ships of opportunity such as fishing vessels, (2) met-ice-ocean forecasts and reanalysis from models (e.g., from CMEMS and INTAROS), (3) fisheries management data (e.g., fisheries stocks, species) from ICES and national sources, and (4) reference data (e.g., bathymetry, economic zones, AIS data).

Based on stakeholder needs, a use case for sustainable fisheries will be implemented using the ingested data and tools for generating customised products. The use case will address two geographic regions, the west coast of Greenland centred around the rich fishing grounds surrounding Disko Bay, and the region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and the Barents Sea. Using the compiled data and developed tools, a regional database of climate, environmental, and fisheries data will be created and made available through an open data repository to support sustainable Arctic Fisheries. This important asset will contribute to the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP) program by providing new data products that can be utilised in digital twin platforms to support decision-making in fisheries management.

The Blue Insight Platform developed by Kongsberg Discovery, Norway, will be part of the Digital Twins of the Ocean (DITTO) program of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development. As part of DITTO and through engagement with other running Digital Twin projects and initiatives such as EDITO, ILIAD, Blue-Cloud2026 and EOOSC, ARCFISH development will follow standards for data exchange and implementation of services and tools in the EU DTO. ARCFISH will prepare training material for using the Blue Insight DTO and organise capacity building events for stakeholders and other SBE projects. Training will be organised in conjunction with project meetings and SBEP events. Furthermore, the regional database, developed services and tools, training and promotional material will be promoted through the iAOS portal from INTAROS, a public project website linked to relevant DTO sites, through the ARCFISH website, and dedicated social media channels. ARCFISH results will also be promoted through the partners' extensive network of Arctic observing and data management, digital technologies, capacity building in ocean literacy, stakeholder interaction and fisheries.

1.2. Organisation of the document

The structure of this document is as follows. Chapter 2 provides a short introduction of how data products can be ingested into the Blue Insight digital platform. Chapter 3 presents the ingestion of a first set of in situ data products from research projects, operational services and monitoring programmes in the regions addressed by the two case studies. Chapters 4-6 showcase ingestion of selected data products from ice-ocean models, satellite data, and ecosystem models covering the areas of interest for ARCFISH, while Chapter 7 presents a first set of data products from the fishing industry. The final chapter, Chapter 8, summarizes the work to prepare a first set of data products for ARCFISH and plans for enhancing the products offered through the Blue Insight platform for the ARCFISH community.

2. Short introduction on the ingestion services

Data may enter the digital twin in several ways. Either from measurements made by the project partners, from in-situ sources or from models developed by the project partners in this or other projects.

Blue Insight natively prioritizes support for Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) interfaces, to be more interoperable with other existing digital twin solutions. A large portion of the scientific community also relies on OPeNDAP (Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol), and specifically the THREDDS server implementation for distribution and integration of model and measurement data in NetCDF format. To facilitate THREDDS, Blue Insight has as part of this project extended the data import features with THREDDS integration functionality to avoid reloading existing accessible datasets into the native databases of the twin.

Figure 1 THREDDS Client Integration diagram

OPeNDAP integration will provide efficient access to remote scientific datasets. This integration enhances our ability to work with large volumes of data without the need for local storage or complete file downloads.

The data is loaded in a few simple steps. First the user will locate the appropriate THREDDS server. The common source used in this project is the IAOS portal (<https://portal-intaros.nersc.no/>), but the implementation is not limited to this source.

From the data loading screen, multiple sources can be accessed. OGC compliant feature APIs, Local data in OGC formats (csv, geojson, parquet etc), Cloud Optimized geotiffs (hosted on a cloud server), or OPeNDAP servers.

Figure 2 The data loading screen integrates several sources.

The solution provides a catalogue exploration service and will drill down into the capabilities of the THREDDS catalogue.

Once the appropriate dataset is located, the user will be presented with a number of choices. The data can be filtered and loaded as points into the scene, the data can be loaded as layers (maps) or the data can be downloaded for further processing through, for instance, the Blue Insight Task Orchestrator fRamework (TOR).

Figure 3 The data loader screen present multiple options for the user.

Figure 4 Sea ice thickness loaded as layers into the scene. If the data has a time component, it can also replay the time.

3. Ingestion services for in situ oceanographic data

3.1. In situ oceanographic data from IOPAN AREX cruises

The main aim of the long-term AREX program and annual cruises, carried by RV Oceania for the last 37 years in the Nordic Seas and Fram Strait, is to recognize and describe processes responsible for changing ocean climate and marine ecosystems in the sub-Arctic and Arctic region with a special focus on the European Arctic. To achieve this goal a large-scale study area, covering the poleward flow of Atlantic water in the eastern Nordic Seas and Fram Strait, has been selected for annually repeated ship-borne measurements on a regular grid. Most of the regularly repeated stations are distributed along several zonal sections, crossing the continental shelf break, and extending towards the deep basin. On the eastern side, the AREX oceanographic sections are limited by the Barents Sea shelf break and the shelf area west and north of Svalbard. To the west, the sections cross the Arctic Front, located above the system of underwater ridges and limiting the extent of Atlantic water in the Nordic Seas.

CTD data (temperature and salinity profiles) from AREX cruises in 2000-2024 and derived data products including e.g. mean properties of Atlantic water or surface layer, mixed layer depth, or integrated ocean heat content have been prepared for ingestion into Blue Insight. Temperature and salinity profiles from AREX cruises can be uploaded into Blue Insight directly from text files in CSV format or from netCDF files after conversion into GeoJSON format. Data from AREX cruises in CSV and netCDF formats is available via the IOPAN OPeNDAP server (Hyrax). In the next step, the gridded fields based on station data will be prepared for visualization in Blue Insight.

Visualization of the mean temperature and salinity of Atlantic water layer, calculated from AREX observations, is shown using Map (Ocean View) and 3D Map functionalities of Blue Insight. (Figure 5 -

Figure 7). In Ocean View individual data sets for each cruise have been uploaded as separate layers which enables selecting one or more visible layers for comparison between years. In 3D Map temperature and salinity data and derived quantities have been uploaded as one file for all years (the collated file has been prepared in the first step; all data are shown on Figure 5 and Figure 6). Data from individual years (cruises) can be seen using time filtering functionality of 3D Map (Figure 7)

Figure 5 Mean temperature of the Atlantic layer measured during the AREX cruises and shown for stations occupied in 2019 and 2023 using Blue Insight Ocean View. Note that the colour scale is different for each year.

Figure 6 Mean salinity of the Atlantic layer measured during the AREX cruises and shown for stations 2023 using Blue Insight Ocean View. Other years can be displayed by switching different layers on/off Note that the colour scale is different for each year.

Figure 7 Mean temperature of the Atlantic layer measured during the AREX cruises and shown for all stations occupied in 2000-2023 using Blue Insight 3D Map. For each station the full set of associated variables can be displayed by selection the station dot with the cursor. Time filter in the lower bottom corner shows time of measurements and allows for selecting a subset of data. The background colour shows ocean bathymetry (GEBCO), available as a separate layer in 3D Map.

3.2. In situ oceanographic data from Copernicus MDS (CORA analysed fields, CORA Near Real Time dataset)

Copernicus Marine In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre (In Situ TAC) products: INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_OA_MY_013_052 and INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_OA_NRT_013_002 were generated by the Coriolis team (the Data Centre and the Research & Development team) in Brest, France, providing global Temperature and Salinity observation datasets and objective analysis gridded fields at different time scales. The second one is a Near Real Time product (NRT) while the first one (also called CORA Analysed fields, see Cabanes et al., 2013 and Szekely et al., 2019) is a reanalysis of these NRT datasets in delayed mode.

The system is based on a statistical analysis method (objective analysis, Bretherton et al., 1976) developed and maintained at LOPS (Laboratoire d'Océanographie Physique et Spatial, Gaillard et al., 2012): the In Situ Analysis System (ISAS). It is performed on the datasets extracted from the Coriolis database for data quality control and producing gridded scalar fields. This system allows presenting a synthesis and a validation of the dataset, providing a support for localized experience (cruises), providing a validation source for operational models, observing seasonal cycle and inter-annual variability. It is the In Situ Objective analysis operational nominal product for the Global Ocean. The dataset contains data from

different types of instruments: mainly Argo floats (including ITP), CTD, XBT and XCTD, moorings, drifting buoys and sea mammals.

The geographical selections/subsets of the Copernicus products were downloaded with use of python scripts/Jupyter Notebooks in netCDF format and were further transformed into GeoJSON format. These output files can be accessed via THREDDS server implementation included in the Blue Insight platform.

In the example below monthly fields of temperature (Figure 8) and salinity (Figure 9) at depth of 1m were ingested into the Blue Insight and presented as points with colour indicating the spatial variability in January 2024. In the further steps depth will be integrated as additional dimension to the geoJSON files. Currently, for each depth level datasets were loaded separately but can be displayed together (Figure 10). Currently the used projection is WGS84 (EPSG:4326), it can be switched to polar stereographic (EPSG:3413 or EPSG:3995).

Figure 8 CORA NRT temperature and salinity data at depth of 1m loaded as layers into the scene. Temperature in January 2024 is displayed. The data has a time component and can be shown for other months of 2024.

Figure 9 CORA NRT temperature and salinity data at depth of 1m loaded as layers into the scene. Salinity in January 2024 is displayed. The data has a time component and can be shown for other months of 2024.

Figure 10 CORA NRT temperature data at depth of 1m and 300m loaded as layers into the scene. The datasets have a time component and are displayed for April 2024.

3.3. In situ oceanographic data from Argo floats

Argo float data were integrated through the OPeNDAP service described in Chapter 2. Data for a selected set of floats were integrated, and selected values will be integrated in later deliveries of the project to provide comparison between the model data and the measurements.

3.4. In situ oceanographic data downloaded from GEM

Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) is an integrated monitoring and long-term research programme on ecosystems and climate change effects and feedback in the Arctic (<https://g-e-m.dk/>). Since 1995 the programme has established a coherent and integrated understanding of the functioning of ecosystems in a highly variable climate, which is based upon a comprehensive, long-term inter-disciplinary data collection carried out by Danish and Greenlandic monitoring and research institutions.

The GEM Programme puts around 75 scientists in the field annually to collect data on ecosystem and climate change in Greenland. The database currently covers data from monitoring programmes from Zackenberg (1995-), Kobbefjord at Nuuk (2007-) and Disko (2017-). The well over 1000 parameters are freely available via the GEM Database and used by GEM participants and external scientists to produce scientific papers, scientific assessments, advisory reports, etc.

In Disko Bay, the Arctic station is on the Disko Island in central west Greenland (Figure 11). The location is characterized by a low Arctic, coastal climate with some of the world's largest icebergs drifting by. In the MarineBasis folder, under GEM, measurements from cruise and monitoring stations in Disko Bay can be found and downloaded. Data includes CTD measurements of salinity and temperature, Chlorophyll a, nutrients (NO₃, NO₂, NH₄, Si, PO₄), pH, dissolved inorganic carbon, suspended particulate matter concentration and macroalgae growth.

Figure 11. Map showing the location of the Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) station in Disko Bay, Greenland (yellow point)

As an example, temperature and salinity measurements from the Disko Bay cruises in 2018-2024 have been ingested into Blue Insight. The data sets retrieved from the GEM data base include the following records:

- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2018, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: 9c8590bd-e3fd-4fbc-8e44-91f02ac53b9f] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/75KS-G922>
- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2019, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: 96f92d6b-d114-4897-82de-2e10c7a81772] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/VB94-Y512>
- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2020, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: e8bac97e-ef5b-4f92-83de-f1ed2c7b5d49] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/MF0H-G023>
- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2022, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: 9ede561d-0808-46c1-8bf2-8c48c262eb4d] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/06Y3-CY76>
- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2023, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: de40fe63-78ab-4565-817d-97814741c398] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/CXGE-A291>
- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2024, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: 19fccf13-94f0-4873-9bc4-0c23ded2e601] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/45WA-6G76>

For the upload and visualisation in Blue Insight, the original data files in text format have been converted into GeoJSON format with reformatting geographical coordinates into uniform format (decimal degrees) and selecting relevant variables from the source data files (date, depth, temperature, and salinity for the example shown on Figures 12 and 13). In addition to creating individual GeoJSON files for each year, the integrated temperature and salinity data from all GEM cruises in Disko Bay in 2018-2024 have been collated in one GeoJSON object, allowing to upload all records simultaneously into Blue Insight.

The data conversion tool can be automated through Blue Insight's Task Orchestrator framework, and relevant data conversion scripts will be published on Zenodo at the end of the project. Data products like the converted data from the GEM database will be uploaded to the OGC Feature API of Blue Insight for simplification of the data loading process, this provides a standardized interface for sharing in other OGC Feature compatible digital twin projects.

Figure 12. Visualisation of temperature at the depth of 10 m from all GEM cruises in Disko Bay in 2018-2024 in the Blue Insight. Data from all cruises have been collated into one GeoJSON file. Details for each station can be displayed to show measurement date, depth (while the GeoJSON file includes all measured depths, a single depth can be extracted with a user-defined filter), and measured variables (temperature and salinity).

Figure 13. Visualisation of salinity at the depth of 10 m from GEM cruises in Disko Bay in 2018 and in 2024 in the Blue Insight. Each year of the cruise data is uploaded as a separate layer what allows to display a single year or a combination of different years at the same map. Note that salinity colour scale is different for each year, this will be unified in future version of Blue Insight.

4. Ingestion services for met-ice-ocean model products

4.1. CMEMS Topaz forecast products

A forecast of ice-ocean parameters for the Arctic is produced on a daily basis by the Copernicus Marine Services, for a 10-day period. The forecast is generated by the TOPAZ5 model developed by NERSC and run operationally by the Marine Arctic Monitoring and Forecasting Center (ARC-MFC) operated by the Meteorological Institute of Norway. The forecast contains a number of key ice-ocean parameters such as ocean temperature, salinity, sea ice thickness, sea ice area fraction (Figure 14), and uses a 100-member EnKF assimilation scheme.

ARC-MFC provides access to the TOPAZ5 forecasts through OPeNDAP, enabling selection of specific parameters and sub-setting (in space and time). This allows ingestion of chosen parameters for a given area and time period into Blue Insight. The TOPAZ5 forecasts provide a 10-day forecast of physical ocean parameters and include sea ice parameters generated by the CICEv5.1 model. Data assimilation is done weekly to produce a 7-day ensemble average of the forecast. ARC-MFC provides hourly, 6-hours, daily and monthly mean fields for the TOPAZ5 forecasts. All forecasts are provided in NetCDF-4 format.

Figure 14. Visualisation of sea surface temperature forecast from the TOPAZ5 model in Blue Insight, including trawling activity data from the Brim fishery, marked as short lines in the visualization.

4.2. CMEMS Wind-Wave forecast product

The Copernicus Marine Service produces forecasts of surface wind and wave conditions in the Arctic using the Wave Model (WAM). The forecasts are generated twice per day at 3 km resolution and provide one-hourly 10-day forecast and one-hourly 5-day forecast. The WAM model provides more than 20 parameters, of which significant wave height (Figure 15, peak period and mean direction are the most commonly used. Surface winds and boundary wave spectra from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) and tidal currents and ice from the ARC MFC forecasts (Sea Ice concentration and thickness) were used as forcing fields for the WAM model.

WAM forecasts are provided in NetCDF-4 format and are accessible from the ARC-MFC through OPeNDAP. This allows for sub-setting in space and time, as well as selecting only specific parameters, for visualisation in Blue Insight. Other data, such as trawler paths, can be overlaid on WAM forecasts (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Visualisation of significant wave height forecast from WAM model in Blue Insight loaded from the OPeNDAP servers.

4.3. Overlaying model products in the 3D Scene builder

The primary data ingestion method in this project is through the OPeNDAP integration described in Chapter 2. However Blue Insight also provides a 3D scene builder, and the capacity to ingest relatively large datasets as points to enable filtering features. Figure 16 illustrates how two model data sets can be visualised on top of each other in Blue Insight.

Figure 16 Model forecasts integrated into the Blue Insight 3D Scene builder. Here illustrated by the Arctic Subpolar gyre sTate Estimate (ASTE) and the Disko Bay model datasets.

5. Data ingestion services for remote sensing data

5.1. Ocean parameters from satellite remote sensing

Some data sets were also collected from satellites using remote sensing. We can integrate such data in Blue Insight and compare their values to the model data. Integration can be done using the four methods outlined in Chapter 2. In Figure 17 we have integrated the Copernicus wave data (WAVE_GLO_PHY_SWH_L3_NRT_014_001) product from the Sentinel-6 satellite as data points.

Figure 17 Integration of CMEMS wave data into Blue Insight.

6. Ingestion services for ecosystem model products

Aarhus University has a coupled hydrodynamic-biogeochemical model covering the greater Disko Bay area in west Greenland (Møller et al. 2023, Larsen et al. 2020). The 3D model is implemented in the unstructured marine model framework FlexSem (<https://marweb.bios.au.dk/flexsem>). It has a semi-circular open boundary towards the Baffin Bay, where it is forced by interpolated data from the HYCOM and pan-Arctic “A20” models. It includes meteorological, ice-cover and freshwater runoff forcings. The model has a horizontal resolution varying between 2 km in the inner part to 15 km near the open boundary and has been run for the period 2004-2018¹.

As part of the ARCFISH data ingestion service, model data output from the setup has been transferred to Kongsberg to be included in the Blue Insight platform DTO (e.g. Figure 18). AU has provided an integrated C++ and Python API to read the binary native format that stores the unstructured model output and examples of how to read, interpret and present the time varying unstructured 3D data. AU has provided 3D monthly values of temperature, salinity, chlorophyll, primary production, net primary production, light attenuation (Kd), nitrate, phosphate, microzooplankton production, and mesozooplankton production for 2017.

¹ Møller EF, Christensen A, Larsen J, Mankoff KD, Ribergaard MH, Sejr MK et al. The sensitivity of primary productivity in Disko Bay, a coastal Arctic ecosystem to changes in freshwater discharge and sea ice cover. EGU sphere 2023 <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-19-403-2023>

Figure 18 Disco Bay model integrated into the Blue Insight Environment.

7. Ingestion services for fishery-dependent and resource management data

Blue whiting is a small cod fish of great importance for the Icelandic economy. It has historically been used for production of fish meal, for production of aquaculture feed, and fish oil, or in some instances for human consumption. Recent industry trials have shown great potential for further value creation from blue whiting, providing an opportunity for processing the fish for human consumption.

In the first meeting with Brim and TrackWell, it was clear that the fishing company was mostly interested in pelagic species in connection with the digital twin. Especially blue whiting, where the fishing grounds can be difficult to locate, where the species prefers open seas and deep waters. During their lifecycle, blue whiting exhibit seasonal migratory patterns. In the summer months, they are commonly found in deeper waters in the North but during the spawning season, which usually peaks between March and April, they usually migrate to shallower continental shelf areas to reproduce.

Fishing companies are interested in knowing the best location to fish at any given time. Blue whiting is constantly on the move and it can be a challenge for captains to locate the fish schools. Environmental factors such as salinity, temperature and zooplankton availability can influence the distribution and abundance of blue whiting. A combination of VMS data and fishing data (e.g. catch information) with other relevant data (e.g. ecosystem and resource management data) can have huge potential for stakeholders (e.g. fishing companies, research communities, resource managers, and surveillance sectors). Below are some examples of data integration into the Blue Insight from different fisheries data sources (e.g. Figures 19, 20 and 21).

Figure 19 Vessel movement and trawl data from Trackwell displayed in Blue Insight

Figure 20 Replay functionality displaying the fishing vessel movement

Figure 21 The combination of ecosystem modelling and fisheries data

8. Summary and next steps

During the first year of the ARCFISH project, partners have prepared selected data sets and started to ingest these in the Blue Insight digital platform. This includes several in situ oceanographic data sets and forecasts from different ice-ocean and ecosystem models, examples of remote sensing products, as well as sample data from the fisheries sectors. Data ingestion has leveraged the capabilities of Blue Insight to import data from standard formats (e.g. CSV, GeoJSON, GeoTIFF) and the ability to read data through the OPeNDAP standard protocol to enable sub-setting of large datasets. The datasets have been visualised using the 2D Ocean Viewer and the 3D Scene builder components of Blue Insight, where reference data of global bathymetry and regular map data are pre-loaded and can be used as background layers.

Selected in situ data products from research projects (AREX), operational services (NRT and analysed fields from Copernicus MDS) and environmental monitoring programmes (GEM) were ingested in Blue Insight. Plans for extending these data products include, among others, gridded fields based on station data from AREX cruises and new in situ oceanographic data from Argo floats. The data conversion tool for ad in situ data from the GEM database, can be automated through Blue Insight’s Task Orchestrator framework, and relevant data conversion scripts will be published on Zenodo at the end of the project.

Examples of forecasts from three met-ice-ocean models were integrated, including two forecasts of physical ice-ocean parameters from CMEMS, and a reanalysis of ice-ocean parameters from the University of Texas. The CMEMS TOPAZ5 and WAM model forecasts are publicly available and provided through the OPeNDAP protocol in NetCDF-4 format. This allows for direct integration in Blue Insight through its current ingestion services. The OPeNDAP access to CMEMS model products will also be used to generate new data products based on available model forecasts and reanalyses for the two case study regions in ARCFISH. These products will be based on stakeholder requirements (Gunnlaugsson and Maar, 2025) and

requirements for products to be developed in WP3 (New data products and regional database). Data ingestion services for selected new products will be implemented in the TOR of Blue Insight, i.e. packaged as Docker containers that can be run in the TOR.

To illustrate integration of satellite data products, we ingested an example of a wave data products from the Sentinel-6 satellite. This product was ingested as data points. Other satellite data products provide raster layers, similar to model products shown in this document. Such satellite data products, e.g., for sea surface temperature, will be considered for ingestion in Blue Insight, depending on stakeholder needs.

For the Disko Bay ecosystem model, data products from more years will be made available for the Blue Insight platform. Further, ecological indices for fisheries will be developed in WP3 and provided as maps for stakeholders. A new shrimp model will be used to evaluate important areas for the shrimp fishery and to highlight the year-to-year variability under different environmental conditions.

We have explored ingestion of sample data from the fishing industry, including examples of vessel track data and catch information. Additional fisheries data will be explored together with other relevant data, such as ecosystem and resource management data, to offer new data products. Such products and enhanced Blue Insight services have large potential value for fishing companies, research communities, and resource management and surveillance sectors. Furthermore, Integration of vessel data in NRT into Blue Insight is foreseen. Blue Insight is currently being used in the One Ocean Expedition 2025 – 2026 (<https://www.oneoceanexpedition.com/>) to gather all collected data, making these data available to participants onboard Statsraad Lehmkuhl, and transferring data to NMDC for long-term storage.

9. References

- Bretherton F.P., Davis R.E., Fandry C.B., A technique for objective analysis and design of oceanographic experiments applied to MODE-73 (1976) Deep-Sea Research and Oceanographic Abstracts, 23 (7), pp. 559 – 582, DOI: 10.1016/0011-7471(76)90001-2
- Cabanes C, Grouazel A, von Schuckmann K, Hamon M, Turpin V, Coatanoan C, Paris F, Guinehut S, Boone, C, Ferry N, de Boyer Montégut C, Carval T, Reverdin G, Pouliquen S, Le Traon, P.-Y. 2013. The CORA dataset: validation and diagnostics of in-situ ocean temperature and salinity measurements. Ocean Science. DOI:10.5194/os-9-1-2013
- Digital Curation Centre (DCC), 2018. DIGITAL CURATION CENTRE: DCC TEMPLATE. Online at (accessed 17 February 2020) https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/template_export/1638514350.pdf
- Gaillard F. 2012. ISAS-Tool Version 6: Method and configuration. DOI:10.13155/22583
- Gunnlaugsson, Valur N., and Maar, Marie (2025). Requirement specification. ARCFISH Deliverable 1.2. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15195612>.
- Larsen J, Mohn, C, Pastor AR, Maar, M (2020). A versatile marine modelling tool applied to arctic, temperate and tropical waters. PLoS One 15(4): e0231193. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0231193>
- Møller EF, Christensen A, Larsen J, Mankoff KD, Ribergaard MH, Sejr M, Wallhead P, Maar M. (2023) The sensitivity of primary productivity in Disko Bay, a coastal Arctic ecosystem to changes in freshwater discharge and sea ice cover. Ocean Science 19: 403-420. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-19-403-2023>
- Szekely T, Gourrion J, Pouliquen S, Reverdin G. 2019. The CORA 5.2 dataset: global in-situ temperature and salinity measurements dataset. Data description and validation. Ocean Science Discussion. DOI:10.5194/os-2018-144
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, Ij. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Scientific Data, 3(1), 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Co-funded by the European Union through the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership, The Research Council of Norway (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark, The National Centre for Research and Development, Poland (NCBR); The Icelandic Centre for Research, Iceland (RANNIS); and Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT). Views and opinions expressed, however, are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the national research agencies. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

Endorsed by:

2021
2030 United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development